

Diabetes, Blood Viscosity, and Cardiac Afterload

*Robert M. Peters

Zucker School of Medicine, 500 Hofstra Blvd., Hempstead, New York, 11549 USA

*Corresponding author: [Robert M. Peters, MD, FACC \(emeritus\), MBA](#)

Zucker School of Medicine, 500 Hofstra Blvd., Hempstead, New York, 11549 USA

Abstract

Hyperglycemia has been found to be associated with increased whole blood viscosity. Thicker, more viscous blood causes more resistance to left ventricular ejection, thus increasing cardiac afterload. This may cause adverse cardiac effects in diabetic patients.

Keywords: *Diabetes blood viscosity cardiac afterload.*

Introduction:

Cardiac afterload is the resistance that the left ventricle (LV) encounters to the ejection of stroke volume during systole [1]. There are many factors that can increase afterload, including rheologic factors such as increased blood viscosity [2]. Several studies have shown an association between hyperglycemia and increased blood viscosity [3]. This increase in afterload may have adverse consequences, especially in diabetics, as they are predisposed to heart disease, including diabetic cardiomyopathy [4].

Methods and Results:

Several studies have found increased blood viscosity in diabetes, including pre-diabetes [5]. Increasing afterload causing greater resistance to LV ejection may result in left ventricular hypertrophy, LV chamber enlargement, and eventually decreased LV systolic function with congestive heart failure (as seen in diabetic cardiomyopathy). Also, increased viscosity has been associated with increased arterial stiffness which can increase LV afterload even further. Reducing blood viscosity has been found to reduce the LV after load [6].

Discussion:

The above considerations add further support for good diabetic control to promote cardiovascular health in diabetics. It might be useful to periodically monitor the blood viscosity in diabetics. Further studies in this area may be of considerable interest.

References:

1. Little RC, Little WC. Cardiac preload, afterload, and heart failure. Arch Int Med 1982; 142(4):819-822. Doi 10.1001/archinte.1982.00340170179027.
2. Alery T, Deterich J, et al. Physical properties of blood and their relationship to clinical conditions. Front Physiol 2022; 13:85-129. PMC9298661. Doi 10.3389/fphys.2002906768.
3. Mushtaq M, Mateen M, et al. Hyperglycemia associated blood viscosity can be a nexus stimuli. Clin Hemorheol Microcirc 2019;71(1):103-112. PMD 30056416. Doi 10.3233/CH-180426.
4. Smati H, Qadeer Y. Diabetic cardiomyopathy: what clinicians should know. Amer J Med 2025;138(3):387-395. Doi 10.1016/j.amjmed.2024.10.026.
5. Carallo C, Scavelli F, et al. Blood viscosity in subjects with normoglycemia and pre-diabetes. Diabetes Care 2014;37(2):488-492. Doi.org/10.2337/dc13-1374.
6. Pop G. Reducing cardiac after-load by lowering blood viscosity. Cor et Vasa 2016; 58(4):374-378. Doi 10.1016/j.crvasa.2015.10.001